

Effect of time of split application of K on grain and straw yield (t ha⁻¹) of rice.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield		Straw yield	
	Feb-Jun	Jul-Nov	Feb-Jun	Jul-Nov
Control (T1)	3.4	3.3	4.8	4.4
Entire basal K (T2)	4.4	4.4	6.6	6.4
K 7d earlier than N at T and PI (T3)	6.5	6.4	8.2	8.1
K + N at T and PI (T4)	5.1	4.9	7.0	6.7
K 7d after N at T and PI (T5)	3.8	3.6	5.3	5.0
K 7d earlier than N at T and K + N at PI (T6)	5.7	5.5	7.2	7.0
K 7d earlier than N at T and K 7d after N at PI (T7)	5.1	4.9	7.6	7.4
K + N at T and K 7d earlier than N at PI (T8)	5.2	5.0	7.3	7.1
K + N at T and K 7d after N at PI (T9)	4.3	4.1	6.6	6.3
K 7d after N at T and K 7d earlier than N at PI (T10)	4.2	4.0	6.5	6.1
K 7d after N at T and K + N at PI (T11)	4.2	4.0	6.7	6.4
CD (p = 0.05)	0.544	0.405	0.834	0.625

^a T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation, K + N = joint application of K and N.

Grain yield was positively correlated with NH₄-N at maximum tillering in the February-June ($Y = 1.51 \times -1.85$, $r = 0.89^{**}$) and July-November seasons ($Y = 1.49 \times -1.91$, $r = 0.91^{**}$). Application of K before N presumably suppressed fixation of NH₄⁺ from applied fertilizer

because selective exchange sites in the 2:1 layer clay minerals were occupied by K⁺. On clay soils with high K⁺ and NH₄⁺ fixation potential, rice yields and N recovery efficiency can be increased by applying K fertilizer 1 wk before N topdressing. ■

Changes in ammoniacal (a), nitrate (b), and available nitrogen (c) due to time of split application of potassium.

Effect of Biozyme and NPK on rice yield

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Biozyme is a commercial product produced from *Ascophyllum nodosum*, a seaweed alga known to be rich in cytokinin and auxin precursors, enzymes, and hydrolyzed protein. Farmers apply it in the field to enhance growth and yield of crop by effecting better utilization of nutrients.

We conducted a field trial during the 1993-94 wet season to investigate the effect of Biozyme granules in combination with NPK on yield performance of rice at the BHU research farm. The trial consisted of nine treatments: control (i.e., no Biozyme or NPK) (T1); 15 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 120-60-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (100% fertilizer) (T2); 15 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T3); 20 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T4);

20 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T5); 40 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T6); 40 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T7); 50 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer (T8); and 50 kg Biozyme ha⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer (T9).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. N, P, and K were applied as urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash, respectively. All of the P, K, and Biozyme were applied basally, while N was applied in three splits (in 1:2:1 ratio) during transplanting, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation. In treatments 6, 7, 8, and 9, Biozyme was applied in two equal splits, at transplanting and 30 d after transplanting (DAT).

The variety was Early Monsoori, a medium-duration cultivar. Soil was slightly alkaline (pH 7.4), has low available N (210 kg ha⁻¹) and P (11 kg ha⁻¹) but medium K (179 kg ha⁻¹) content, and 0.32% organic C. The field was kept flooded throughout the growing period.

All treatments recorded significant increases in number of spikelets panicle⁻¹, panicles m⁻², and grain and straw yield over the control in both years. An increase in yield with an increasing dose of Biozyme + fertilizer was observed up to the 40 kg Biozyme + 100% fertilizer ha⁻¹ treatment, after which a decreasing trend was noted. T6 produced a significantly superior yield compared with T2 and T3; the rest remained statistically on par with each other. It was further observed that the yield gap between 100 and 50% fertilizer doses along with different doses of Biozyme was considerably reduced. A similar trend was also found in all other yield-attributing characters. The stimulatory effect of Biozyme was most probably due to the presence of cytokinin and auxin precursors, which resulted in elevated cellular energy and more effective tillering. The addition of Biozyme at 20 kg ha⁻¹ with 50% of the recommended NPK dose could save as much as Rs 690.35 ha⁻¹ over 100% fertilization. ■

Yield-attributing characters of rice as affected by Biozyme and NPK. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1993-94.

Treatment	Panicle length (cm)		Panicle weight (g)		Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		Spikelets m ⁻² ('000)		1,000-grain weight (g)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
Control (no Biozyme and no NPK)	22.60	21.34	3.21	3.83	173.17	190.10	29.13	36.00	16.87	16.58
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer ^a	23.34	22.04	3.69	3.90	187.30	210.32	40.44	50.63	16.97	17.01
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.62	22.22	3.51	3.84	183.40	199.62	38.75	47.34	16.93	16.99
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	22.92	22.66	4.10	4.22	197.23	220.30	45.04	55.41	17.07	17.10
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	22.86	22.26	4.00	4.18	195.13	212.53	42.11	51.25	17.02	17.08
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	22.85	22.00	4.29	4.47	202.63	225.87	51.37	65.79	17.60	17.85
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.74	21.65	4.17	4.37	199.33	215.40	48.17	60.83	17.33	17.58
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	23.74	22.46	3.98	4.11	189.23	207.05	38.72	48.08	17.20	17.33
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	23.11	22.38	3.74	4.00	181.60	203.21	45.07	46.81	17.00	17.23
S _d ⁻	0.62	0.61	0.80	0.33	7.23	8.17	0.74	0.83	0.43	0.39
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	15.35	17.32	1.58	1.75	ns	ns
CV (%)	3.27	3.38	11.97	10.29	13.33	13.46	3.35	3.71	3.09	4.58

Treatment	Panicles m ² (no.)		Filled spikelets (%)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
Control (no Biozyme and no NPK)	175.31	200.11	81.12	84.34	2.1	2.2	3.8	4.2
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer ^a	227.33	255.73	82.67	86.83	2.9	3.2	4.8	6.0
15 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	218.44	249.42	81.57	86.18	2.8	3.2	4.6	5.8
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	243.62	261.15	85.03	87.17	3.3	3.5	5.4	6.4
20 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	231.23	255.80	83.19	86.99	3.2	3.4	5.3	6.2
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	265.19	309.43	85.96	89.96	3.5	3.7	5.2	7.0
40 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	258.92	297.37	85.49	88.89	3.4	3.6	5.6	6.6
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 100% fertilizer	218.65	247.13	84.96	86.93	3.0	3.3	5.0	5.1
50 kg Biozyme ha ⁻¹ + 50% fertilizer	264.91	245.56	84.08	86.77	2.9	3.3	5.0	5.9
S _d ⁻	18.85	21.22	3.35	3.21	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.5
LSD (0.05)	39.96	44.99	ns	ns	0.6	0.5	1.5	1.2
CV (%)	12.13	13.34	4.87	5.07	11.2	12.0	13.9	11.7

^a 120-60-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Effects of fertilizer and green manure on survival and productivity of detached deepwater rice plants

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Deepwater rice plants sometimes get detached from the soil during the vegetative stage due to damage by crabs and other organisms. They then float in water. The survival of such plants depends on nodal roots that draw nutrients from the floodwater. Nodal roots can appear within 24 h

of stem detachment and improve the survival and productivity of deepwater rice.

Detached deepwater rice plants (128 d old) having only nodal roots were floated in concrete tanks containing 2400 liters of water. Treatments consisted of applying various fertilizers and "burying" of *Sesbania aculeata* plants in water (see table). The aim was to maintain a nutrient concentration of 5 or 10 ppm N in water.

Temperature and dissolved O₂ content of the water were measured at 6:20 a.m. and at 4:00 p.m. Average temperature was 29 °C in the morning and 31 °C in the afternoon. Water pH was measured at 9:00 a.m. and at 3:00 p.m. It increased by 0.5-1.0 unit in the

afternoon. After application of NP/NPK fertilizers, pH increased to within the 9.3-9.7 range due to algal growth. Decomposition of green manure lowered water pH, maintaining it between 7.2 and 8.2.

Dissolved O₂ concentration was generally higher in the afternoon than in the morning. In the presence of decomposing green manure, dissolved O₂ was 0.0-0.2 ppm in the morning and 1.0-6.6 ppm in the afternoon.

At crop maturity, four samples were harvested from each tank. There was a positive response to applied nutrients (see table). Application of NP gave NPK gave the best yields and were superior to application